

Digital Marketing as a Tool of Mass Communication for health and wellness Entrepreneurs of South Odisha

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ABSTRACT

Modern age makes use of Digital Marketing techniques for mass communication in most of the cases. Not just has it reduced the marketing cost by its effectiveness, but it has also enabled the business owners to reach the customers in a better way. It also aids in analysing and reviewing data on customers behaviours so that the wellness entrepreneurs can layout more proficient strategies for achieving business objectives. (Sheoliha et al 2023). There have been several studies done at health sector leverage on Digital Marketing. That being said of the numerous digital marketing option available to rural health sector the exploration is still yet to begin in India.

Purpose of study: *The present study identifies the factors affecting the usage of Digital Marketing for Business Promotion by the wellness entrepreneurs of Southern Odisha.*

Method: *The study utilizes hybrid model of UTAUT and TOE. It analyses the response of 386 respondents from the region. regression analysis was used to test hypotheses.*

Outcome: *The study, concludes that Performance expectations, Effort expectations, Technological, Organisational and Environmental factors are the factors that show their influence on utilisation of Digital marketing among health and wellness entrepreneurs of South Odisha.*

Keywords: *Digital marketing, health and wellness entrepreneurs, rural entrepreneurs, wellness entrepreneurs of India, South Odisha.*

Introduction

According to Smith with his colleagues (2012): "Digital marketing (DM) is the promotion of services or products through different forms of digital media. As digital platforms, they allow for active information and stocking control. Digital Platforms Influenced the Evolution of Consumer Marketing Mobile telephone and laptop adoption have fuelled a rapid expansion in online advertising. Indeed, more than \$50 billion was spent for advertisements on social media (SM) platforms in 2017 [Solakis, K et al 2022]. In 2018, 44% (273 Bilion

\$) of advertising revenue (629 Billion \$) in the world came from digital advertisement [Nhuvira, C.E.; Dorasamy, N. 2021]. By targeting certain demographics, marketing directly through digital media can meet growth targets like getting more revenue, brand exposure, customer contact, and lead generation. This, in turn, led to a rise in advertising budget disparities [Eid, R.; El-Gohary, H.2013].

Direct messaging has always made it easy to sell/buy goods online, whatever the free delivery method. DM represents a diverse set of products, services, and marketing techniques. This type of marketing utilizes different forms of digital media.

Digital communications with stakeholders can happen at any point in time. DM aims to attract new customers and provide a means of engaging with the company [He, W.; Wang, F.-K.; Zha, S. 2014]. Digital marketing can include aspects such as search engine optimisation, cost-per-click, short message marketing, affiliates marketing, social media optimisation and marketing, email campaigns and internet based advertising.

The majority of the Digital Marketing studies are focused on companies and organisations that are larger, not smaller [Ritz, W.; Wolf, M.; McQuitty, S 2019]. Small businesses must develop mobile optimised websites, and they require external experts to help manage them. 51.90% of small US businesses lack a website because of economic limitation [Pandey, N et al 2020,]. Small companies in US usually having no or websites due to cost constraints [Nuseira, M.T.; Aljumahb A. 2020].

Indeed it is important for organizations to remain abreast about the new gadgets. particularly so for SMEs; small and medium enterprises have; in emerging nations [Ritz W, Wolf, M. McQuitty, S., 2019]. India, is striving to bolster the adoption of technology (ICT) in businesses. It can, hence, conclude that a sturdy ICT infrastructure is extremely vital to the competitiveness of SMEs.

The access to Internet is facilitated with development of many digital infrastructures which is allowing people to use Internet more easily. but that does not mean that digital communications has become uniformly better. (Ofcom, 2016, p3). A number of remote rural places in rich economies are being left behind in the provision and capabilities of digital infrastructures (e.g. Riddlesden and Singleton, 2014; Philip et al., 2017).

Numerous previous studies have focused on examining the factors that influence SMEs' and startups' and drove them to adopt digital marketing and the corresponding factors in developed and developing nations. The restrictions challenge of infrastructural, economic, socio-economic condition and educational imperfection in rural area (Goel R. 2024) makes it essential to study the determinants of Digital Marketing acceptance by Rural Entrepreneurs.

The motivation for this study was to understand the same for the wellness entrepreneurs of south Odisha based on UTAUT theory through quantitative approach. The given data is Primary data gathered through convenience sampling and the exploratory factor analysis is carried out through SPSS and then the hypothesis is tested through linear regression analysis which was done on SPSS.

This study is an effort to fill the gap in the existing scholarship by providing insights through focusing on digital marketing in rural South Odisha which could be replicated for the other parts of the country. This work contributes to a scientific understanding of digital marketing for academics and managers, entrepreneurs, and business owners. On the other hand, this study which assists start-up companies in health and wellness to recognize the factors impact the acceptance of digital marketing provides them opportunity to grow and resolve diversity of problems.

2. Literature review:

2.1: Marketing Digitalisation

Digital marketing means, the process of using technology in marketing so that you can understand your

customers. 'Online marketing' refers to the use of gadgets like smartphones, computers and other devices to reach out to clients through social media, websites, apps and other channels. Digital Marketing: There Is A High Potential It deals with the importance of online marketing which is gaining insights into how customers engage with the latest technology and leveraging that insight to drive more business for the organization. This allows the user to address prospective clients more effectively. The days of businesses from developed countries not knowing or not being aware of digital marketing are well done now. In order to do well the business would require both offline methods as the demand will probably call for both (Bala & Verma, 2018).

2.2 Digital Marketing in Indian Market

India has the second-largest proportion of people using the internet – with nearly half (49.15%) of its population on internet (692 million people) after China (1.05 billion people, 74.36%) [explodingtopics 2023]. No surprise thus, that the Indian online advertisement and shopping industry is increasing an annual basis. Millennials and Generation Z spend an increasing amount of time and money on digital platforms, influencing what their clientele prefers.

Internet can say that Books, electronics, travel, financial services, cloths and cosmetic-products are the common buy products and services. Currently, the Internet makes up only a small percentage of India's GDP, but stores expect a boom in the Internet (Schneider, 2020).

2.3 Benefits of Digital Marketing to Wellness Entrepreneur

Digital Marketing also has altered how marketing practices work in more ways than one. It has brought so many advantages to the users that today a business without digital marketing is thought to be an unfeasible. Here are some advantages that Digital Marketing offers to the entrepreneurs:

Improve allotment to the customers from different channels in like meta, Google, Instagram and the like. Digital marketing allows you to channel directly to the consumers mobile or computer across the globe. Improved targeting of the customers as digital marketing allows you to track the target population on the basis of their online actions and interests logged, thus filtering the disinterested people in the marketing level only. (Fachrurazi, F et al 2022). It also makes the marketing costs decently graded for wellness entrepreneurs by exhibiting the products on virtual platforms eliminating printing and distribution costs as in the traditional ways. (Fachrurazi, F et al 2022). You have better marketing analytics for subsequent followup and retargeting. This aids in going a layer deeper in market. According to the old-fashioned marketing campaigns, comparatively very less efforts needed. One can do Digital Marketing sitting with computer / Mobile in any corner of the globe at any point of time. Immediate customer service by Providing support to the customers to resolve their queries and underscoring their importance (Yamini & Chand, 2020). Health and wellness entrepreneurs with lesser budget and resources can embrace these changes for a Better Competitive Advantage (Kano, K et al 2022)

3: Theoretical Framework:

For several decades, the study of human-technology interaction has been predominately concerned with identifying the determinants of system acceptability. According to the Reasoned Action theory (TRA) the intention of anyone of performing a particular behaviour is strongly altered because of attitudes towards the behaviour and other unsaid rules, assessed based on a social pressure of performing the behaviour or abstain from engaging in it [Ajzen, I.1991]

The TRA was then applied by Azjen [Ajzen, I.; Madden, T.J. 1986] in his work on their theory, which ultimately culminated in the development of the technology acceptance model (TAM; Davis et al. 1989).

The model of technology acceptance (TAM), which measures how quickly new technologies are accepted, is considered a reliable tool. As a result, many research projects have started to explore pros and cons, and the

enabling factors of information and communications technology (ICT) use by older persons. However, this curiosity led to a numerous theories, technology acceptability models and practical utilisation in the past few decades [Marangunić, N.; Granić, A.2015]. The TAM is widely used as measurement instruments in academic research [Petrovčić, A.; Petrić, G.; Manfreda, K.L.2016, Hardill, I.; MacDonald, S. 2000]. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was introduced first by Fred Davis [Davis, F.D.; Bagozzi, R.P.; Warshaw, P.R.1989], based on the theory of reasoned action (TRA) proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen, and Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour (TPB) [Ajzen, I.1991]. The most accepted paradigm which is used widely to predict and illuminate the effects of people's adoption of technology is [Guner, H.; Acarturk, C.2020]. In related research, basic Model of Technology Acceptance (TAM) identifies perceived utility and perceived ease of implementation (use) as core and unique elements determining the decision whether or not to adopt a technology[Hardill, I.; MacDonald, S. 2000, Venkatesh, V.et al 2003]. They also mediate in the complex relationship between system-coated constructs (external constructs) and the expected usage of the system (attitude and behavioral intention). Little studies have suggested the adapted use of the extended forms of TAM to fit the specific objectives of a study. Longer versions of the Models of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) like [Ahmad, M.O.; Markkula, J.; Oivo, M. 2013, Hogeboom, D.L et al 2010] which includes additional variables such as expectancy of efforts required to use technology, difficulty to learn how to use technology, effect of peer and society, etc., have been found to be striking better fit for their purpose of study. According to blending the many technology models with the innumerable TAM models, the refusals and foundations of unification of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT): identify the most important TAM2 and TAM3 [Venkatesh, V.; Thong, J.Y.; Xu, X.2012, Venkatesh, V. et al 2003, 2016]. Underlying the TOE framework is a consistent set of empirical research grounded in a solid theoretical base. Hence, the powerful either or both that are being applied in fields of ICT innovation. A good choice in research examining IT adoption from an organisational point of view is the TOE framework proposed by Alatawi et al (2013).

Considering the current research requirement, we are taking the factor combinations stated in UTAUT and TOE as reference for our study [28, 29]. The factors considered for the study were Performance expectancy, Efforts required, and the Technological, Organisational and Environmental context.

3.1: Performance expectancy

Satisfaction performance model is used to describe the degree to which an individual expects the design of his surroundings should support him in completing his daily duties efficiently and profitably [Venkatesh, V et al 2003, Ghalandari, K. 2012]. The utility of the technology is called performance expectancy [Chao, C.-M.2019, Nikolopoulou, K.et al 2021]. It makes information accessible at any time and from any location through social interaction. Performance expectations has the highest importance as predictor of a user's intention to accept M-technology [Onaolapo, S.; Oyewole, O.2018]. According to [1], performance expectations for the older generation are heightened along with their ambitions to make use of M-technology. The scalable variables we considered here are, perceived relative advantage (of usage of Digital Marketing), Relevance (of usage of Digital Marketing)to the business goal, and perceived risk (in usage of Digital Marketing).

Hypothesis 1: Performance expectancy influences the adoption of Digital Marketing among wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

3.2: Efforts Expectancy

Effort expectancy, in a theoretical context, concerns the amount of perceived benefit from a system with less sever psychic work [Venkatesh, V et al 2003, Milošević, et al 2015]. According to Alraja et al. 2016Effort expectancy = user-friendliness + self-efficacy. A sane individual has a thorough awareness of the IT fundamentals and perks to be able to effectively implement and embrace technology, as well as certainty in the

way it aids them in addressing their wants and needs [Abdallah, N.; Abdallah, O.2021; Bohra, O. 2021, Maiga, G.; Namagembe, F. 2014]. As mentioned by Milošević et al., self-efficiency and simplicity in using, are major factors that greatly impacts the user decision whether of accepting or rejecting the system. Milosevic, D.; Andrei, S.; Vishny, R.W. 2015]. Effort expectations essentially determine how persons feel about the use of devices [Mcmanus, P.; Standing, C.; Zanolli, R. 2009]. Hence, the factors in question are Complexity, Compatibility and the availability of vendors.

Hypothesis 2: Effort expectancy is directly association with the use of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

3.3: Technological Context

As reported by previous studies on the IT use that employed the TOE theory (e.g., Grover, 1993; Iacovou et al., 1995; Thong, 1999), technological aspects of every organization will normally describe the features of the innovation that affect the adoption of different IT innovation of an organization (Chau & Tam 1997; Thong 1999). The three Characters that has been considered in this study are IT related Infrastructure available at firm , Technical Knowhow, and perceived trend (in respect of usage of Digital Marketing as a medium to promote business).

Hypothesis 3: Technological factors are associated with the use of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

3.4: Organisational Context

Organisational context which describes an organisations characteristics influencing the adoption of technology by any organisation may affect any type of adoption of technology (Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990). The presence and access of skilled and educated staff, consultants, and technology related service providers also contribute to innovation (Rees et al., 1984). Literature in consideration, this study focus on 4 of the potential variables related with global digital marketing success – Firm Size (in terms of team size), Financial support available, Training and Support (provided by the top management) and Team motivation level (for utilisation of digital marketing).

Hypothesis 4: There is a relationship between the Organisational factors and the utilisation of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

3.5: Environmental Context

The environmental context comprises of the industry structure, the presence or absence of the technical service providers and the dogmatic atmosphere. Industrial structure has been studied for example through the intense competition that encourages the spread of innovation (Mansfield, 1968; Mansfield et al., 1977).

Kamath and Liker (1994) state that the strength of firms in the value chain is important as these firms can dictate to their counterparts to innovate. The system of technological support feeds again in innovation. But paid out to the highly qualified workers, innovations that have the possibility of saving labor are more often demanded (Globerman, 1975; Levin et al., 1987). Finally, government regulation may have either a positive or a negative impact on organisations, depending on whether it stimulates or inhibits innovation (Baker, 2011).

Hence the variables considered under this factor are competitive pressure, composite Participation and support from government.

Hypothesis 5: Environmental factor is directly and positively related in Digital Marketing use by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

4. Methodology

The items that are used in the construct of this study are derived from earlier studies. This is to maintain the construct validity. For example, we draw items of Performance expectancy from Rogers (1983), Fichman, R. G., & Kemerer, C. F. (1997), and Dinev, T., & Hart, P. (2006). Organisation context; taken from Chong et al (2005) and Eze, S. C et al (2020). The factors of the variables of efforts expectancy is adopted from Rogers (1983) Technological Factors: adapted from Kimaro, H. C., & Nhampossa, J. L. (2005); Rogers (1983); and Xu, X., Zhang, W., & Barkhi, R. (2010). Environmental context items are shown in Chong et al (2005).

The factors identified in literature are summarised in the below table.

Factors	Reference
Performance expectancy	Dinev, T., & Hart, P. (2006), Fichman, R. G., & Kemerer, C. F. (1997), and Rogers (1983),
Organisational Context	Eze, S. C et al (2020). and Chong et al (2005)
Efforts required	Rogers (1983).
Technological variables	Rogers (1983), and Xu, X., Zhang, W., & Barkhi, R. (2010) Kimaro, H. C., & Nhampossa, J. L. (2005),
Environmental variable	Chong et al - (2005)

The study questionnaire was developed and data collection: Responses were collected on 5 point likert scale where scoring is done as value scored as follows:

1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree, and 5= Strongly Agree.

Sampling was done in the districts of Gajapati, Koraput, Kalahandi, Kandhamal, Malkangiri, Nabarangpur, Nuapada, and Rayagada, in southern Odisha, data was collected between Q4 2023. The total collected responses is 423 and only around 386 were considered fit for analysis.

5. Analysis

The result of each the regression analysis is as follows:

H1: Performance expectancy influences the adoption of Digital Marketing among wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	545.132	1	545.232	32.527	.000 ^b
Residual	5255.055	384	13.685		
Total	5700.187	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Performance_Expectancy

H2: Effort expectancy is directly association with the use of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	61.532	1	61.532	4.329	.038 ^b
Residual	5636.634	384	14.669		
Total	5700.167	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Efforts_Required

H3: Technological factors are associated with the use of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	521.018	1	521.018	37.815	.000 ^b
Residual	5179.169	384	13.503		
Total	5700.167	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Technological_context

H4: There is a relationship between the Organisational factors and the utilisation of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	472.472	1	472.472	34.625	.000 ^b
Residual	5228.615	384	13.414		
Total	5700.176	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Organisational_Factors

H5: Environmental factor is directly and positively related in Digital Marketing use by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	457.084	1	457.084	34.434	.000 ^b
Residual	5231.009	384	13.622		
Total	5700.167	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Environmental_Context

Above regression analysis shows, for all the five hypotheses the significance value are <0.05. So we can say that all the hypotheses fail to reject.

6. Results and Discussion:

Regression analysis was then carried out for every hypothesized relationship between each independent and dependent variable. The goal is to not only predict and explain (and also sometimes perform causal inference) by modelling the relationship between the variable.

The output from regression analysis for all 5 variables indicates significant relationships of the independent variables with the dependent variable ($p < 0.05$) (Brereton RG 2019). So, The following hypothesis are accepted.

H1: Performance expectancy influences the adoption of Digital Marketing among wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha - Accepted

H2: Effort expectancy is directly association with the use of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha - Accepted

H3: Technological factors are associated with the use of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha - Accepted

H4: There is a relationship between the Organisational factors and the utilisation of Digital Marketing by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha. - Accepted

H5: Environmental factor is directly and positively related in Digital Marketing use by wellness entrepreneurs from southern Odisha. - Accepted

7. Conclusion:

The purpose of conducted analysis is to determine the impact of Performance expectancy, Effort expectancy, Technological factors, Organisational factors, and Environmental factors on the acceptance & adoption of digital marketing in health & wellness enterprises of South Odisha. For the purpose of the research on Primary Data, 5 Hypothesis have taken for the same to identify. The collected data are analysed using the methods of EFA and regression analysis, which results in determination of the impact of independent variables on dependent variables. The research outcome reveals that if provided with the required infrastructure and support by the government, the wellness entrepreneurs are ready to accept and implement the digital marketing avenues. Also, the technical knowhow about these digital marketing tools must promoted. So, it may be suggested to the decision makers of the district to provide a greater number of digital infrastructure facilities and (problem wise based) possible promotional subsidies for the rural sectors. In the process the Digital marketing industry leaders needs to beautify the tools, make it easy to use with basic affordable adverting plan. Using confirmatory factor analysis, the research can be advanced further to identify the model fit. The Present study covers only the rural health and wellness entrepreneurs of South Odisha. Since India is a nation with diversified culture and beliefs so a more in-depth study can be conducted to identify the determinants which influence the adoption of Digital Marketing among health and wellness entrepreneurs of different rural regions of the nation.

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